

SPEECH ACT EXPRESSION IN CHILDREN'S QUASIDIALOGUE

N.K.Musayeva

NavDPI Maktabgacha ta'lim kafedrası katta o'qituvchisi

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Annotation: this article comments on the fact that the quasidialogical speech process is staged and performed by children, and the speech that occurs in such a game situation is the implementation of specific stages in the occurrence of acts.

Keywords: speech, quasialog, locutive, illocutive, perlocutive, phonetic, morphological, syntactic, subject, target.

Аннотация: в данной статье высказывается мнение о том, что квазидиалогический речевой процесс инсценируется и разыгрывается детьми и что в возникшей в такой игровой ситуации речевой ситуации реализуются специфические этапы возникновения актов.

Ключевые слова: речь, квазидиалог, локатив, иллокутив, перлокутив, фонетический, морфологический, синтаксический, предметный, целевой.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada kvazidialogik nutq jarayoni bolalar tomonidan sahnalashtirib ijro etilishi va bunday o'yin vaziyatida vujudga kelgan nutq aktlarning yuzaga kelishida o'ziga xos bosqichlar amalga oshirilishi haqida fikr-mulohaza bildirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nutq, kvazidialog, lokutiv, illokutiv, perlokutiv, fonetik, morfologik, sintaktik, predmet, maqsad.

Since the speech act is a type of activity, its analysis uses essentially the same categories necessary for describing and evaluating any action: subject, goal, method, means, result, conditions, success, etc. Speech appears both as a product of speech activity and as a means of achieving a specific goal. Speech activity may achieve its goal, be successful or fail, depending on the existing circumstances or conditions. In order to be successful, the speech act must be appropriate for the purpose. Otherwise, the speaker will fail as a communicative incompetent.

M. Qurbonova also gives valuable opinions about the place of the speech act in pragmalinguistics, its research, main issues, classification, and pays special attention to the issue of using types of speech acts in children's speech activity. According to the scientist, although the type of speech act to use in the process of communication depends on the communicative goal of the speaker, the psychological and emotional state of a person, gender, age also have a significant impact on the choice of the type of speech act. What type of speech act children

choose in the process of communication depends on their psychological state, especially age characteristics.[5.]

From a pragmatic point of view, the correct interpretation of the receiver is important for the effectiveness of the communication in order to achieve the intention and goal of the addressee.

In the scientific sources studied above, it is mainly emphasized that the three-stage activity of the speech act is performed: locative, illocutionary and perlocutionary actions.

Accordingly, below, we analyze the manifestation of these three speech movements in children's quasi-dialogic speech.

It is known that each replica in a quasi-dialogical speech has a form and content. The formative aspect is its phonetic, morphological and syntactic structure. The content side includes two: propositional and illocutionary aspects. The illocutionary function of speech corresponds to a certain speech act (confirmation, question, encouragement, request, etc.).

In particular, every sentence in a quasi-dialogic speech has the same locutionary act action as any other sentence. Because the locative act is the pronunciation, utterance, that is, the act of speaking. In children's quasi-dialogic speech, it is possible to observe the expression of the locative act and its internal signs (phonetic, phatic, rhetic). For example: Dilshad, 9 years old. He wants to collect toys and invent:

Mashinani olamiz va yangi moslama o'rnatib, yorug'lik tezigiga chiqaramiz. Bu mashina ilg'or mashina bo'lishi kerak, to'g'rimi?

- *To'g'ri.*

- *Qani, buuufff.*

- *Eh, o'xshamadiku, boshqatdan qilamiz. // Qani? Kim yangi moslama o'rnatib, yorug'lik tezigiga chiqaradi?*

In this quasi-dialogic speech, the child pronounces the sentences according to the norms of the language and brings out the locative act. It is noteworthy that the full effect of the phonetic act in children's speech also depends on their age. Sometimes, it is possible to observe violation of pronunciation standards in young children. In our opinion, if the child's pronunciation norms are violated, but his thoughts are understandable to others, that is, if the child as an addressee can convey his thoughts, then the locative act is valid. Because it is natural for young children to break pronunciation standards for some reasons. For example: Habiba, 4 years old. He

puts his doll to sleep. – *Allloo-la, uxab tosin, shiyinim. Tatta tizim allaayoyoyo. Uxa, dedim, ana bappa telyapti. Tet bapa, tet.*

From this quasi-dialogical speech, it is known that the girl's voice is lowered, the voice is exchanged *uxlab//uxab, qolsin//tosin, shirinim//shiyinim, katta//tatta, qizim//tizim, ket//tet* violation of pronunciation norms is observed.

Considering the child's age, this can be considered a temporary condition. M. Kurbanova also emphasizes that "locution act in children's speech can be formed sometimes under the requirement of speech norms, sometimes without following them". [5]

The goal of the speaker's communication changes or continues depending on the attitude of the interlocutor, so the harmony of dialogic speech is subject to purposeful activity. Intentional analysis studies the aspects of speech activity related to the speaker's purpose and desire, and this analysis is important in the study of the speech act.

Due to the fact that the goal and its achievement are expressed in replicas corresponding to various speech acts, the illocutionary act is also expressed through replicas in quasi-dialogic speech. For example: Bunyod, 9 years old. "Mol Doctor" performs a staged quasi-dialogue. Quasisherik - toys:

- *Kettim, xamsiyani qo'zichog'i kasal ekan shuni davolashga. Bular ham moliga hech yaxshi qaramas ekan-da. Men kelguncha tinchgina o'tiringlar, beboshlik qilmay. Shunday deb qatorlashtirib terilgan o'yinchoqlarini bir-bir yana to'g'rilab qo'yadi.*

Flying Spider-Man up: *Siz keginizcha orilarni qo'rib turay, iltimos, zerikdim,-deydi.*

- *Yaxshi, ehtiyot bo'l, faqat. Chaqib olmasin. Men darrov qaytaman. Hamsiya! Hamsiya-yuyuyu! Hormang! Mana men keldim. Qo'zichani ayag'iga nima bo'ldi? // taxtakach bilan bog'laymiz, kel o'zimga qoravoyim. Onangni aytganini qimay, ko'p dirkillagansan-da.*

Kechiring, boshqa sakramayman.

- *Bo'ldi, ayag'ing yaxshi bo'sa boqamiz, yangi yil bayramiga.... Yo'g'yeye xafa bo'lma, hazillashdim. Seni hech kimga xafa qildirib qo'ymayman.*

During this game, the child's wishes and goals are revealed through various illocutionary acts. For example: "*Kettim, xamsiyani qo'zichog'i kasal ekan*", "*Mana men keldim*", "*Zerikdim*" act of confirmation in sentences like, "*Men kelguncha tinchgina o'tiringlar, beboshlik qilmay*", "*Ehtiyot bo'l, faqat*", "*Chaqib olmasin*", "*Men darrov qaytaman*", "*Onangni aytganini qimay, ko'p dirkillagansan-*

da" warning in sentences like, "*Siz keginizcha orilarni qo'rib turay, iltimos*" please in the sentence, "*Qo'zichani ayag'iga nima bo'ldi?*" a question in the sentence, "*Kechiring, boshqa sakramayman*" I'm sorry, "*Bo'ldi, ayag'ing yaxshi bo'sa boqamiz, yangi yil bayramiga*" desire in the sentence, "*Seni hech kimga xafa qildirib qo'ymayman*" the speech act of promise is expressed in the sentence.

Although the child plays the role of a mole doctor in this quasi-dialogical speech, at the end of the dialogue, the child reveals his "I". That is, according to the information I heard from adults "*Yangi yil bayramiga boqib so'yamiz*" the act of desire is immediate "*Seni hech kimga xafa qildirib qo'ymayman*" promise, care turns into a speech act. This indicates the innocence of the children's world, their special love for animals, and it is shown in their speech unknowingly. O. Pochepsov and Sh. Safarov also propose to divide the intention into two parts, i.e. "initial intention" and "resulting intention". Although in this quasi-dialogic speech, the "initial intention" begins with expressing the desire-goal of adults by imitating their speech, in the "resultative intention" the child's own goal: the inner desire to care for animals is manifested.

It seems that in most cases, a general illocutionary act is hidden in children's quasi-dialogic speech. The child expresses his opinion that he could not openly express to adults by staging a quasi-dialogue. Children's quasi-dialogic speech is a process that freely expresses all the child's feelings and desires, and differs from the usual speech activity of adults. Because the appearance of a quasi-dialogue depends on a certain situation and environment, and in such situations, the child is free and open to imaginary interlocutors, and makes better use of his language capabilities. Because he will not have a live dialogue partner who will correct his speech and react. He interacts with his favorite toys more closely and freely than adults. Since children's quasi-dialogic speech is a process that reflects the child's innocence, acts of advice, sarcastic affirmation, warning, and promise are rare in this speech. It can be said that since the children's quasi-dialogic speech is controlled by a single subject, the implementation or confirmation of the illocutionary act expressed through the speech replica is easier in the response replica. That is, the content consistency and harmony between replicas prevails over the dialogic speech of adults.

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